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3 **Microplastic-Induced Gut Dysbiosis and Metabolic Alterations in Juvenile**
4 **European Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*): A Multi-omics Approach**

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39 **Abstract**

40 Environmental microplastics (MPs) are increasingly recognized as emerging
41 contaminants with the potential to disrupt intestinal homeostasis in marine organisms.
42 However, most experimental evidence is based on pristine particles rather than
43 environmentally weathered forms. This study investigated the intestinal effects of
44 environmentally derived microplastics (EMPs) in juvenile European seabass
45 (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) using an integrated multi-omics approach. Fish were exposed
46 for five days to two concentrations of EMPs (0.5 and 1 mg/g of feed), followed by
47 analyses combining histological, transcriptomic, metabolomic, and metagenomic
48 endpoints. EMP exposure led to significant particle accumulation in gut tissues,
49 predominantly consisting of small polyethylene fragments. Gene expression and
50 immunofluorescence analyses revealed activation of p53 and Caspase-3 mediated
51 apoptosis together with NF-κB and IL-6 driven inflammatory signalling, indicating
52 concurrent oxidative and immune stress. Untargeted metabolomics identified marked
53 alterations in lipid metabolism, redox regulation, and amino acid turnover, consistent
54 with mitochondrial dysfunction and impaired energy homeostasis. Parallel
55 metagenomic profiling revealed subtle but coherent shifts in gut bacterial communities,
56 with enrichment of pollutant-tolerant taxa such as *Acidovorax* and *Halioglobus* and
57 reduction of beneficial commensals such as *Ligilactobacillus*. Multi-omics data
58 integration demonstrated a coordinated restructuring of microbial and metabolic
59 networks underlying host physiological stress. Collectively, these findings highlight the
60 intestine as a primary target of microplastic toxicity and provide mechanistic insight
61 into early biological responses to environmentally realistic microplastic exposure in
62 marine fish.

63 **Keywords:** Microplastics; *Dicentrarchus labrax*; Apoptosis; Inflammation;
64 Metabolomics; Gut microbiota.

65

66 **Introduction**

67 Plastic pollution has emerged as a critical environmental challenge and is now
68 recognized as a pervasive threat to marine ecosystems(Galloway et al., 2017; Gola et
69 al., 2021; X. Li et al., 2023). Among the different forms of plastic debris, microplastics
70 (MPs) have attracted particular attention because of their persistence, ubiquity, and
71 ability to interact with biological systems(Wright et al., 2013; Zitouni et al., 2021). MPs
72 are commonly defined as synthetic polymer particles smaller than 5 mm that arise
73 either as primary particles manufactured for industrial applications or as secondary
74 fragments derived from the progressive degradation of larger plastic items under
75 sunlight, oxidation, and mechanical abrasion (Fotopoulou and Karapanagioti, 2015).
76 Global plastic production has exceeded 410 million tonnes annually, resulting in the
77 continuous discharge of microplastics into aquatic environments through wastewater,
78 runoff, and atmospheric fallout (Jambeck et al., 2015; Plastics Europe, 2024). Because
79 of their small size, hydrophobicity, and chemical stability, MPs are readily ingested by
80 aquatic organisms and can accumulate within tissues, thereby facilitating
81 bioaccumulation and trophic transfer across marine food webs(Farrell and Nelson,
82 2013; Avio et al., 2015; Galloway et al., 2017).

83 Once in the marine environment, microplastics do not remain chemically stable for
84 long. Sunlight, oxygen, and microbial activity gradually reshape their structure,
85 producing particles very different from the pristine materials typically used in laboratory
86 work. Continuous exposure to ultraviolet radiation weakens the polymer chains, while
87 biofilms and other microbial layers change the surface texture and increase its
88 chemical reactivity. Through these processes, microplastics acquire a greater ability
89 to bind metals, hydrocarbons, and a wide range of organic pollutants present in
90 seawater(Fotopoulou and Karapanagioti, 2015; Rummel et al., 2017; Schmidtman et
91 al., 2025). The altered fragments, often described as environmentally derived
92 microplastics (EMPs), combine aged polymers with the contaminants that adhere to
93 them, forming complex and highly reactive particles. Studies have shown that such
94 weathered plastics interact more readily with biological membranes and
95 macromolecules than unaltered particles, which may intensify their harmful effects
96 (Hamed et al., 2021; Zitouni et al., 2021). Experimental research in fish and
97 invertebrates links EMP exposure to oxidative stress, mitochondrial impairment, and
98 inflammation, indicating that aging in the natural environment can substantially

99 increase microplastic toxicity(Hamed et al., 2021; Jovanović, 2017; Zitouni et al.,
100 2021). Yet the molecular pathways that connect these physicochemical changes to
101 altered metabolism in fish are still not clearly defined.

102 The European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) is a marine teleost widely distributed
103 along the eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts and represents one of the most
104 commercially important species in aquaculture. Its broad ecological tolerance and
105 well-characterized physiology make it an excellent biological model for evaluating the
106 impact of environmental contaminants in marine ecosystems (Barboza et al., 2018;
107 Granby et al., 2018; Zitouni et al., 2021). Previous investigations have shown that
108 exposure to microplastics can interfere with growth, intestinal morphology, and
109 immune performance in this species, indicating its sensitivity to particulate
110 pollutants(Barboza et al., 2018; Hamed et al., 2021; Montero et al., 2022). Because
111 *D. labrax* inhabits coastal areas where plastic debris accumulates, it provides a
112 realistic framework for assessing both ecological and toxicological consequences of
113 environmentally aged microplastics under near-natural conditions(Granby et al., 2018;
114 Matias et al., 2024).

115 The present study examined the short-term intestinal responses of juvenile *D. labrax*
116 exposed to environmentally collected microplastics using an integrated multi-omics
117 approach that combined targeted gene expression, immunofluorescence,
118 metabolomic, and metagenomic analyses. This experimental design made it possible
119 to characterize the physicochemical properties of the collected particles and evaluate
120 their accumulation within intestinal tissues while also identifying the main metabolic
121 and inflammatory pathways influenced by exposure. Particular attention was given to
122 the relationship between shifts in the gut microbial community and changes in host
123 metabolism, since these interactions are increasingly viewed as key mediators of
124 microplastic-induced intestinal dysfunction. By coupling molecular, metabolic, and
125 microbial endpoints, the study offers new mechanistic insight into the biological effects
126 of environmentally realistic microplastics and highlights early intestinal responses that
127 may serve as sensitive indicators of sublethal stress in marine fish.

128 **2.Materials and Methods**

129 **2.1. Microplastics and Diet Preparation**

130 EMPs were collected in July 2021 from the sandy beach of Sidi Salem, Bizerte,
131 following the protocol developed by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric
132 Administration (NOAA), as described in Zitouni et al., 2021 (Zitouni et al., 2021). EMPs
133 were visually sorted by shape, colour, and size using a stereomicroscope (MOTIC-
134 SMZ-168-TL, Germany) equipped with a digital camera. Polymer composition was
135 confirmed by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), with spectral matching
136 performed using the KnowItAll® Bio-Rad ID Expert 2021 database. Representative
137 particles were then ground with an electric grinder, and fragments smaller than 100
138 μm were isolated using a sieve. Additional structural and elemental analyses were
139 carried out by Raman microspectroscopy (RMS) and scanning electron microscopy
140 coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM/EDX). A stock suspension
141 of the EMPs was prepared in distilled water and mixed with TetraMin® flakes to
142 produce experimental diets containing 0.5 mg/g (C1) and 1 mg/g (C2) of EMPs. Diets
143 were prepared 24 hours in advance and stored at 4 °C until use.

144 **2.2. Experimental Design**

145 Juvenile European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), 120 days post-hatching (dph),
146 were obtained in February 2023 from a commercial fish farm (Aquaculture Tunisienne,
147 Sousse, Tunisia) and transported to the laboratory in aerated seawater containers. At
148 the start of the experiment, fish had an average total length of 4.8 cm (\pm 0.3) and body
149 weight of 1.4 g (\pm 0.2 SD). Fish were randomly distributed into three experimental
150 groups (n = 150 per group): a control group (C0) not exposed to MPs and two
151 treatment groups exposed to EMPs at concentrations of 0.5 mg/kg (C1) and 1 mg/kg
152 (C2) feed. Exposure concentrations of 0.5 and 1 mg/kg food were selected because
153 aqueous exposure did not guarantee reliable particle uptake in early life stages, and
154 the mixed polymer composition of environmental microplastics prevented accurate
155 conversion of weight-based doses to items per volume. Fish were housed in separate
156 tanks under controlled conditions (UV-filtered, well-aerated seawater, 20°C, 36%
157 salinity). One-third of the water volume was replaced daily to maintain water quality.
158 Fish were fed a commercial diet three times daily, supplemented with MPs for the
159 treatment groups. Based on the feeding behaviour of juvenile European sea bass, the
160 daily feeding rate was set to 1% of the fish's body weight (w/w). The exposure period
161 lasted for 5 days.

162 **2.3. Sample Collection and Preparation**

163 At the end of the five-day exposure period, fish were euthanized using an overdose of
164 MS-222 (100 mg/L) and rinsed with Milli-Q water to eliminate external contaminants.
165 Gut tissues were carefully dissected and processed for different analyses. For
166 metabolomic, metagenomic, and chemical characterization, tissues were pooled in
167 groups of nine per sample, while transcriptomic analysis was conducted on pools of
168 three. Samples for metabolomic and metagenomic analysis were immediately stored
169 at -80°C, whereas those designated for chemical analysis were preserved at -20°C.
170 Gut tissues for histological analysis were immediately fixed in 4% formalin. All
171 procedures were conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines set by the Research
172 Ethics Committee in Life and Health Sciences (CER-SVS) of the Higher Institute of
173 Biotechnology of Monastir, under the approved protocol CERSVS/ISBM 007/2025.

174 **2.4. Microplastic extraction and characterization**

175 The extraction and quantification of EMPs in gut tissues followed the protocol outlined
176 by Phuong et al (Phuong et al., 2018) and later refined by Zitouni et al (Zitouni et al.,
177 2020). In brief, pooled gut samples were digested with a 10% (w/v) potassium
178 hydroxide (KOH) solution at 60 °C under constant agitation for 24 h to achieve
179 complete tissue breakdown. The digested material was then transferred to separatory
180 funnels and left to decant at room temperature for 4 h, allowing the lighter MPs to
181 separate from denser residues. A subsequent density separation step with 50% (w/v)
182 potassium iodide (KI) solution was used to further isolate MPs from remaining mineral
183 particles. Supernatants were filtered sequentially through cellulose nitrate membranes
184 (0.45, 1.2, and 3 µm pore sizes, Ø = 47 mm; Whatman, UK). Retained MPs were
185 analysed by RMS using four co-scans with a 785 nm excitation laser. Polymer
186 identification was confirmed against the BioRadKnowItAll® Informatics System
187 Raman ID Expert (2018) library. To control for contamination, three procedural blanks
188 were processed alongside samples, none of which showed detectable MP spectra.

189 **2.5. RT-qPCR Analysis of Stress-Related Genes**

190 Total RNA was isolated from pooled gut tissues (three individuals per pool; n = 3 pools
191 per treatment group) using the acid phenol–chloroform procedure (Chomczynski and
192 Sacchi, 1987) combined with TRI-Reagent (Sigma-Aldrich). RNA quality was verified
193 by UV spectrophotometry and agarose gel electrophoresis. Downstream processing
194 followed the approach of Banni et al (Banni et al., 2014). Expression levels of
195 apoptosis-related genes (*p53*, *BAX*, *BCL2*, *CASP3*, *CYCS*) and inflammatory markers

196 (NF- κ B, IL-6) were quantified using SYBR Green I chemistry (EvaGreen® dye; Bio-
197 Rad). Primer sets (Table S1) were designed in Beacon Designer v3.0. Data were
198 normalized to GAPDH and 18S, according to Banni et al.(Banni et al., 2016). qRT-PCR
199 was performed with three biological and three technical replicates per sample. Cycling
200 conditions included 95 °C for 30 s, followed by 40 cycles of 95 °C for 10 s and 60 °C
201 for 20 s. Group mean comparisons were evaluated using a random reallocation test
202 (Pfaffl et al., 2002).

203 **2.6. Immunofluorescence Analysis**

204 Immunofluorescence analysis was employed to investigate the expression levels of
205 apoptosis-related markers (Bax, Bcl-2, Caspase-3, P53, Cytochrome-C) and
206 inflammation markers (NF κ B-p65, IL-6) in gut tissues. Gut tissues from control and
207 EMPs-exposed groups were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA), embedded in
208 paraffin, and sectioned at 5 μ m thickness. Tissue sections were deparaffinized,
209 rehydrated, and subjected to antigen retrieval using 0.5 M glycine. Non-specific
210 binding sites were blocked with a solution containing 20% goat serum and 5% bovine
211 serum albumin (BSA) in PBS. Sections were incubated overnight at 4°C with primary
212 antibodies (1:100 dilution;TableS2), followed by washing and incubation with
213 secondary antibodies (1:500 dilution; Table S2). Nuclear staining was performed using
214 DAPI (H-1200-10; Vector Laboratories, Peterborough, UK). Fluorescence microscopy
215 was used to detect antibody localization, and fluorescence intensity was quantified
216 using ImageJ software.

217 **2.7. Metabolomic Analysis**

218 For untargeted metabolomic analysis, a total of 45 fish (five per replicate, three
219 replicates per group) were used. Intestines from every five fish per replicate were
220 pooled for metabolite extraction, and samples were stored at -80 °C until processing.
221 Extraction and analysis were performed following the protocol described by
222 Boughattas et al(Boughattas et al., 2024), with minor adjustments. Briefly, tissue
223 metabolites were extracted with 80% methanol containing 0.1% formic acid, sonicated,
224 centrifuged, and filtered through 0.22 μ m cellulose filters. The extracts were analysed
225 by high-resolution mass spectrometry using a Q-Exactive Focus Hybrid Quadrupole-
226 Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer coupled to a Vanquish UHPLC system equipped with a
227 HESI-II probe. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a water–acetonitrile
228 gradient and data acquired in full-scan mode (100-1000 m/z) under positive ionization

229 mode. Raw data were processed with MS-DIAL (Tsugawa et al., 2015), and differential
230 features were identified using Agilent Mass Profiler Professional (version B.15.1).
231 Compounds annotation was based on tandem MS fragmentation pattern and isotopic
232 profiling (monoisotopic mass, isotopes spacing and ratio) achieving a level 2 of
233 annotation (putatively annotated compounds), as referred to COSMOS standards in
234 metabolomics (Salek et al., 2013). QC samples were prepared by pooling equal
235 aliquots from all individual samples and randomly injected throughout the sequence.
236 QC samples were analysed using data-dependent MS/MS fragmentation (N=9 top
237 ions) with collision energies of 10, 20, and 40 eV (Salehi et al., 2023).

238 **2.8.16S amplicon sequencing of fish gut microbiota**

239 Microbial community analysis was performed on gut samples of juvenile *Dicentrarchus*
240 *labrax*. Total DNA was extracted using the DNeasyPowerSoil Kit (Qiagen, Germany)
241 and quantified with the Quant-iT™ HS dsDNA Assay Kit (Invitrogen, UK) and a Qubit
242 2.0 fluorometer. The bacterial and archaeal communities were assessed through 16S
243 rDNA amplicon sequencing targeting the V3–V4 regions. The detailed amplification,
244 sequencing, and bioinformatic pipeline followed the protocol previously described by
245 Boughattas et al (Boughattas et al., 2024). Briefly, amplicons were generated using
246 bacterial primers 343F/802R and archaeal primers 344F/806R, sequenced on the
247 Illumina MiSeq platform, and processed through standard pipelines including chimera
248 removal, taxonomic assignment against the SILVA database, and downstream
249 diversity analyses. Alpha diversity was calculated using Simpson's Diversity Index and
250 Good's coverage, while beta diversity was assessed using PCA and Canonical
251 Correspondence Analysis (CCA) in R with the Vegan package.

252 **2.9 Integration of Metagenomic and Metabolomic Datasets**

253 Metabolomic and metagenomic datasets were normalized by centering and log-ratio
254 transformation prior to integration. Multi-omics analysis was conducted using the
255 DIABLO framework implemented in the *mixOmics* R package (v6.20.0) (Rohart et al.,
256 2017). Model optimization involved tuning the number of latent components and
257 selected variables through repeated, stratified cross-validation. The best-performing
258 model was chosen based on the Balanced Error Rate (BER), while variable selection
259 was refined by comparing models under different ℓ_1 penalties.

260 **2.10. Statistical Analysis**

261 All statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism software (version
262 9.3.0). Data are expressed as mean values accompanied by standard deviation (SD).
263 Normality of distributions was evaluated with the Shapiro–Wilk test before further
264 testing. When normality was confirmed, differences among groups were assessed
265 using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test. Statistical
266 significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

267 Concerning metabolomics, feature abundance was log₂-transformed, normalised to
268 the 75th percentile, and then baselined against the median in the dataset. Thereafter,
269 hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) was used to unsupervisedly evaluate patterns
270 among treatments. To this aim, a fold-change (FC) heat map, Euclidean distance, and
271 Ward’s linkage rule were used. Datasets were then analysed by supervised
272 multivariate modelling in SIMCA 17 (Umetrics, Malmo; Sweden) using orthogonal
273 projection to latent structures discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA). The models were
274 cross-validated (CV-ANOVA; $p < 0.05$), and outlier excluded by Hotelling’s T₂, and
275 then model parameters (R²Y goodness-of-fit, and Q²Y goodness-of-prediction) were
276 recorded. Permutation tests were used to exclude overfitting, (n=100). Afterwards,
277 Variable Importance in Projection (VIP) analysis identified metabolites with the highest
278 discriminant potential score (VIP > 1.1). Finally, Volcano plot analysis ($p < 0.05$; Fold
279 Change > 1.0) was run to identify statistically differential metabolites. Metabolite
280 enrichment analysis was performed using Chemical Similarity Enrichment Analysis for
281 metabolomics (Barupal and Fiehn, 2017).

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284 **3.Results**

285 **3.1. Microplastic Characterization in the Stock Solution**

286 SEM micrographs and EDX analyses provided detailed information on the morphology
287 and surface composition of the microplastic particles used in this experiment (Figure
288 S1: I-a-a1;b-b1;c-c1). Three principal morphotypes were observed: films (I-a-a1),
289 fragments (I-b-b1)and fibres (I-c-c1). Films appeared thin, flexible, and relatively
290 smooth, consistent with the degradation of packaging materials. Fibres were
291 elongated and showed frayed ends and surface irregularities typical of synthetic

292 textiles or fishing gear. Fragments exhibited angular edges and cracked textures,
293 reflecting advanced mechanical and photo-oxidative weathering.

294 At higher magnification, surface pitting and fractures were evident, particularly on
295 fibres and fragments, confirming long-term environmental exposure. EDX elemental
296 mapping revealed (Figure S1;l-a2-b2-c2) predominant peaks for carbon (C) and
297 oxygen (O), with traces of silicon (Si), chlorine (Cl), aluminium (Al), calcium (Ca), iron
298 (Fe), and sodium (Na).. Collectively, the morphological and elemental patterns
299 confirmed that the collected material represented environmentally derived,
300 heterogeneous, and weathered microplastics.

301 Quantitative assessment identified 4607.33 particles per 100 µg distributed among
302 three size fractions and five polymer types. The smallest fraction (1.22–0.45 µm)
303 accounted for the majority of particles, consisting of 32.31 % polyethylene (PE), 28.12
304 % polyethylene terephthalate (PET), 17.60 % polypropylene (PP), 12.97 % low-density
305 polyethylene (LDPE), and 8.97 % high-density polyethylene (HDPE). Similar but
306 slightly shifted proportions were found in the intermediate (3–1.22 µm) and larger (> 3
307 µm) fractions (Figure S2). Across all classes, PE predominated, followed by PET and
308 PP, indicating the dominance of small, chemically diverse, and environmentally aged
309 particles in the stock suspension.

310 **3.2. Microplastic Accumulation and Characterization in Seabass Gut Tissues**

311 Raman microspectroscopy quantified microplastic retention in the intestinal tissue of
312 juvenile *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Figure S1-II-A;B). Control fish displayed background
313 levels averaging 9.25 particles per gram of tissue, whereas exposed fish showed
314 substantially higher concentrations, reaching 99.21 particles/g in C1 and 140.28
315 particles/g in C2. This confirmed active ingestion and intestinal accumulation of
316 environmentally aged microplastics.

317 All polymer types present in the stock suspension (PE, PET, PP, LDPE, HDPE) were
318 detected in the intestinal samples of exposed fish. Controls contained mainly PE and
319 LDPE, consistent with residual background exposure. Among the size classes, the 3–
320 1.22 µm range displayed the greatest abundance, followed by > 3 µm and 1.22–0.45
321 µm fractions. For the > 3 µm fraction, polymer composition in C1 was 33.78 % PE,
322 21.03 % PET, 19.31 % PP, 12.24 % LDPE, and 13.61 % HDPE; in C2, 29.98 % PE,
323 25.71 % PET, 19.85 % PP, 12.95 % LDPE, and 11.51 % HDPE. The persistence of

324 PE and PET across all fractions indicates their higher stability and likelihood of
325 retention within digestive tissues.

326 **3.3 RT-qPCR Analysis of Stress-Related Genes**

327 RT-qPCR Analysis were performed to evaluate the molecular response to
328 environmentally derived microplastic exposure (Figure 1). The stress-responsive gene
329 *p53* was significantly up-regulated in exposed groups compared with controls.
330 Similarly, pro-apoptotic markers *bax* and *casp3* showed higher expression levels,
331 indicating activation of apoptotic signalling cascades. In contrast, the anti-apoptotic
332 *bcl2* transcript remained unchanged, suggesting a limited compensatory response.
333 Expression of *cytc*, a component of the mitochondrial apoptosis pathway, also
334 increased relative to the control.

335 Inflammatory genes *il6* and *nfkb* exhibited elevated gene expression, consistent with
336 activation of pro-inflammatory signalling in intestinal tissue. Collectively, these results
337 demonstrate that short-term exposure to environmentally aged microplastics induces
338 molecular responses associated with both apoptosis and inflammation in juvenile *D.*
339 *labrax*.

340 **3.4 Immunofluorescence**

341 Immunofluorescence assays revealed significant alterations in the expression of both
342 apoptotic and inflammatory markers in the gut tissues of *Dicentrarchus labrax*
343 following exposure to EMPs (Figure 2). Bax fluorescence intensity increased markedly
344 in both EMP-exposed groups compared to the control, while Bcl-2 levels remained
345 relatively stable across all conditions. The observed upregulation of Bax, together with
346 unchanged Bcl-2 expression, indicates a shift toward pro-apoptotic signalling
347 pathways in the exposed groups. Similarly, Cytochrome C and Caspase-3 exhibited
348 higher fluorescence intensity in C1 and C2 relative to the control group, reflecting
349 enhanced activation of the intrinsic apoptotic pathway. p53 showed stronger and more
350 widespread fluorescence in the exposed intestines, supporting its role in cellular stress
351 regulation under EMP exposure.

352 Regarding inflammation, both NFκB-p65 and IL-6 displayed increased fluorescence
353 intensity in C1 and C2 relative to controls. In the exposed fish, NFκB-p65 signals
354 appeared not only in the cytoplasm but also within nuclei of intestinal epithelial cells,
355 suggesting activation of the canonical NF-κB pathway. This pattern coincided with a

356 broader distribution of IL-6 immunoreactivity across the mucosal layer, consistent with
357 a local inflammatory response triggered by EMP ingestion.

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370 Fig. 1. Expression profiles of apoptosis- and inflammation-associated genes (p53, CASP3, BAX, BCL2,
371 IL6, NFKB, and CYCS) in seabass intestinal tissue following dietary exposure to EMPs. Experimental
372 groups: control (C0), 0.5 mg/ kg EMPs (C1), and 1 mg/kg EMPs (C2). Relative mRNA levels were
373 normalized to GAPDH and 18S rRNA.

374

375 3.5 Untargeted Metabolomics Analysis

376 Untargeted metabolomic profiling of intestinal tissues revealed marked exposure-
377 related variations in the metabolic profiles of juvenile *Dicentrarchus labrax* following
378 short-term dietary exposure to EMPs. A total of 3,139 compounds were annotated
379 across all samples. Among these, several metabolites were significantly altered (FDR-
380 adjusted $p < 0.05$, $|FC| \geq 2$) in the C1 and C2 groups, respectively, when compared to
381 the control.

382 Multivariate analyses confirmed distinct metabolic signatures across treatments.
383 Unsupervised hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) and principal component analysis
384 (PCA) both separated C1 and C2 from the control group, while supervised orthogonal
385 projections to latent structures discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA) showed complete
386 group separation and strong model performance ($R^2Y = 0.994$; $Q^2 = 0.981$; $p < 0.001$)
387 (Figure 3B-3C-3D).

388 In the C1 group, altered metabolites were mainly associated with alkaloids, glycosides,
389 and plant-derived secondary compounds. Significant decreases were observed for

390 reticuline, isocorydine, and shogaol, whereas certain glycosides showed moderate
391 accumulation.

392 The C2 group exhibited broader changes involving lipid-related metabolites. Several
393 diacylglycerols, phosphatidylserines, and unsaturated fatty acids were reduced in
394 abundance relative to the control. Additional variations were detected in peptide- and
395 indole-derived metabolites, including neuromedin and imidazoquinoline-like
396 compounds.

397 Chemical Similarity Enrichment (ChemRICH) analysis revealed consistent enrichment
398 or depletion patterns among treatment groups. In C1, the altered clusters included
399 glycosides and several secondary metabolite classes (Figure 3C). In C2, the
400 predominant changes occurred in lipid- and peptide-related clusters (Figure 3D).

401 Collectively, these results demonstrate that EMP exposure altered the intestinal
402 metabolome of juvenile European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), characterized by
403 compound-class-specific changes that differ between the two exposure
404 concentrations.

405 **3.6. 16S amplicon sequencing**

406 High-throughput sequencing of intestinal bacterial communities in *Dicentrarchus*
407 *labrax* revealed consistent profiles across treatments, though subtle differences in
408 composition were evident (Figure 4). Alpha-diversity, measured by the Chao1 index,
409 showed no statistically significant differences among groups ($p > 0.05$). A mild
410 reduction in median richness was observed in exposed fish compared with the control
411 (Figure 4-A).

412 Beta-diversity analysis using Bray–Curtis dissimilarity and principal coordinates
413 analysis (PCoA) demonstrated overlapping yet distinct clustering patterns. Samples
414 from control and C1 groups displayed partial overlap, whereas C2 samples formed a
415 loosely separated cluster along the first coordinate axis, explaining 31.5 % of total
416 variance (Figure 4-B). These findings suggest a modest reorganization of the gut
417 microbiota following exposure to environmentally aged microplastics.

418 Taxonomic analysis at the genus level identified *Acidovorax*, *Halioglobus*, *Glaciecola*,
419 and *Ligilactobacillus* as dominant taxa across all samples. *Acidovorax* and *Halioglobus*
420 were relatively enriched in exposed fish, while *Glaciecola* and *Ligilactobacillus*
421 remained more abundant in controls. LEfSe analysis identified these four genera as
422 discriminant taxa with LDA scores above 3.5, supporting the observed compositional

423 shifts despite limited changes in overall diversity. Collectively, these data indicate that
424 short-term exposure to microplastics produced subtle but consistent modifications in
425 gut microbial structure, primarily affecting the relative abundance of opportunistic and
426 commensal taxa.

427 **3.7 Integration between metagenomics and metabolomics**

428 To investigate host–microbiota interactions underlying the intestinal response to EMP
429 exposure, a multiblock data integration approach (sPLS-DA) was applied to the gut
430 microbiota (BAC) and metabolomic (MTB) datasets. The combined analysis showed
431 distinct segregation of both exposed groups (C1 and C2) from the control (C0) along
432 the first component in each block, demonstrating strong covariation between microbial
433 composition and metabolic profiles following EMP exposure (Figure 5-A).

434 Correlation circle plots confirmed tight coupling between discriminant variables across
435 the two omics layers, with strong intra-block correlations ($r > 0.8$) primarily responsible
436 for group separation (Figure 5-B). Metabolomic variables contributing most strongly to
437 C1 included features associated with amino-acid and lipid metabolism, whereas the
438 main bacterial drivers in the BAC block comprised taxa enriched in exposed groups
439 and previously linked to intestinal dysbiosis (*Acidovorax*, *Halioglobus*). C2 captured
440 additional group-specific variation, most evident in the C2 dataset.

441 Clustered heatmap visualization of the top 50 cross-correlated features revealed co-
442 regulated modules that clearly distinguished control and exposed samples (Figure
443 5C). These patterns indicate coordinated alterations in host metabolism and microbial
444 community structure during EMP exposure, supporting the existence of a tightly
445 connected intestinal microbial–metabolic network.

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472 Fig. 2. Immunofluorescence analysis of intestinal tissue from European seabass. Bax, Bcl-2, P53,
 473 Cytochrome-C, IL-6, and NF- κ B appear in green; β -Actin in red; Caspase-3 in red; nuclei stained with
 474 DAPI (blue). The accompanying histograms show fluorescence signal intensity normalized to β -Actin
 475 (except Caspase-3, normalized to DAPI). Treatments that do not share the same letters are significantly
 476 different. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the
 477 web version of this article.)

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480 Fig. 3. Metabolomic profiling of intestinal tissues in juvenile seabass exposed to environmentally derived
 481 microplastics (C1: 0.5 mg/kg diet; C2: 1 mg/kg diet; C0: control group). A) Hierarchical clustering
 482 heatmap of differential metabolites across groups. B) PLS-DA score plot illustrating separation between
 483 treatments. C) ChemRich set Enrichment statistic plot of significantly altered metabolite clusters in C1
 484 relative to control. D) ChemRich set Enrichment statistic plot of significantly altered metabolite clusters
 485 in C2 relative to control. In the ChemRICH plots; each node represents a significantly altered
 486 metabolite cluster, node size corresponds to the number of metabolites within the cluster. Node colour
 487 indicates the proportion of increased (red) and decrease (blue) metabolites within the cluster. (For
 488 interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version
 489 of this article.)

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513 Fig. 4. Gut microbiota diversity and compositional shifts in juvenile seabass following short-term dietary
 514 exposure to environmentally derived microplastics. A) Alpha- (Chao1 index) and B) beta-diversity
 515 (PCoA) analyses, C) relative taxonomic composition, D) LDA scores, and E) 3D ordination illustrate
 516 microbial responses across treatments: C0 (control, unexposed fish), C1 (0.5 mg/kg EMPs), and C2 (1
 517 mg/kg EMPs).
 518

519 **4. Discussion**

520 The present study investigated the intestinal consequences of exposure to EMPs in
 521 juvenile *Dicentrarchus labrax*, providing evidence that weathering and chemical
 522 transformation substantially modify the biological reactivity of microplastic particles.
 523 Once released into aquatic systems, plastics undergo a combination of photochemical
 524 oxidation, hydrolysis, and mechanical fragmentation that alters polymer structure and
 525 increases surface roughness and polarity (Fotopoulou and Karapanagioti, 2015;
 526 Siegfried et al., 2017). These transformations facilitate the adsorption of metals,
 527 hydrocarbons, and persistent organic pollutants, creating complex composite particles
 528 with higher surface energy and stronger affinities for biological interfaces. Such

529 environmental aging enhances particle cell interactions and promotes local oxidative
530 reactions that can disrupt epithelial integrity.

531 Because the gastrointestinal tract constitutes the first site of contact with ingested
532 particles, it serves as a critical target for evaluating the physiological consequences of
533 microplastic exposure in aquatic organisms (Avio et al., 2015; Barboza et al., 2018).
534 Experimental studies in fish and marine invertebrates have shown that microplastics
535 can induce epithelial inflammation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and altered mucosal
536 permeability, often accompanied by oxidative stress and apoptosis in intestinal tissues
537 (Hamed et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2016; Zitouni et al., 2021). However, most of these
538 investigations relied on pristine or industrial microplastics that lack the
539 physicochemical complexity of environmental particles, limiting their ecological
540 relevance.

541 In this context, the present work employed EMPs collected directly from the
542 environment to reproduce more realistic exposure conditions and characterize their
543 short-term intestinal effects using an integrated multi-omics framework. The
544 combination of molecular, metabolomic, and microbial endpoints provides a
545 comprehensive view of the pathways through which aged microplastics disrupt gut
546 homeostasis and reveals association among apoptotic and inflammatory responses,
547 metabolic remodelling, and microbiota alterations in *D. labrax*.

548 **Microplastic Characterization and Intestinal Uptake**

549 SEM coupled with EDX analysis revealed that the MPs used in this study were highly
550 heterogeneous in both morphology and elemental composition. Films, fibers, and
551 fragments were the dominant morphotypes, displaying surface features such as
552 cracks, erosion, and pitting that indicate extensive environmental weathering. The
553 presence of trace elements including Si, Al, Fe, and Cl indicated the adsorption of
554 mineral residues and secondary contaminants acquired during environmental
555 exposure. These alterations, together with oxidized and roughened surfaces, are
556 characteristic of aged MPs and are known to enhance surface energy and reactivity,
557 thereby promoting stronger interactions with biological membranes (Rummel et al.,
558 2017; Bhagat et al., 2022; Binda et al., 2023). The polymeric composition was
559 dominated by PE, PET, and PP, consistent with the prevalence of packaging-derived
560 plastics in marine debris and supporting the environmental realism of the collected
561 material (Barboza et al., 2018; Zitouni et al., 2021).

562 It remains debated whether toxic responses to microplastics are induced by the
 563 particles themselves or by sorbed contaminants (Rochman et al., 2013; Koelmans et
 564 al., 2016). In this study, we intentionally used environmentally derived microplastics
 565 (EMPs) to assess the integrated intestinal response under realistic conditions, without
 566 separating these two contributions. Qualitative comparisons with pristine microplastic
 567 studies (Jin et al., 2019; Wan et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2021) are feasible and support
 568 our findings of gut dysbiosis and metabolic alterations. However, because EMPs are
 569 weathered and carry complex contaminants, direct quantitative comparisons should
 570 be made with caution.

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591 Fig. 5. Integration of metabolomic and metagenomic datasets in juvenile seabass exposed to
 592 environmentally derived microplastics. (A) sPLS-DA plots of bacterial (BAC) and metabolite (MTB)
 593 datasets. (B) Correlation network of significant taxa-metabolite associations ($r > 0.8$, $p < 0.05$). (C)
 594 Correlation circle plot of variable contributions. (D) Hierarchical clustering heatmap of taxa-metabolite
 595 associations across treatments.

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598 Quantification of MPs in intestinal tissues provided clear evidence of ingestion and
599 retention following exposure. While minimal background contamination was detected
600 in control fish, exposed groups contained substantially higher particle numbers,
601 confirming efficient uptake and persistence within the gut. The smallest fraction (3–
602 1.22 μm) was the most frequently retained, suggesting that particle size strongly
603 influences accumulation, possibly through limited peristaltic clearance and enhanced
604 adhesion to the mucosal surface (Babkiewicz et al., 2025). Comparable findings have
605 been reported in *D. labrax* and other teleosts, where fine MPs can embed within
606 mucosal folds or adhere to epithelial cells (Qiao et al., 2019; Zitouni et al., 2021). PE
607 was consistently the most abundant polymer detected in intestinal samples, likely
608 owing to its high environmental occurrence and its hydrophobic affinity for lipid-rich
609 epithelial membranes (de Souza Freire et al., 2023). Altogether, these results
610 demonstrate that environmentally aged MPs, characterized by rough and oxidized
611 surfaces, are readily internalized and retained within the intestinal lumen and
612 epithelium of *D. labrax*, providing a realistic exposure scenario for investigating the
613 molecular and metabolic pathways underlying MP-induced intestinal disturbance.

614 **Cellular and Molecular Responses**

615 The integration of gene expression and protein data demonstrates that
616 environmentally derived microplastics trigger a coordinated activation of apoptotic and
617 inflammatory mechanisms in the intestinal epithelium of *Dicentrarchus labrax*. The
618 concomitant upregulation of *p53*, *bax*, *casp3*, and *cytc*, together with the increased
619 immunoreactivity of Bax, Caspase-3, and Cytochrome C, indicates the engagement
620 of the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway. This pattern is consistent with mitochondrial
621 dysfunction and activation of intrinsic apoptosis, responses frequently associated with
622 microplastic exposure in fish tissues (Jin et al., 2018; Qiao et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2023).
623 The preservation of *bcl2* expression, coupled with elevated Bax levels, suggests a
624 shift in the Bax/Bcl-2 equilibrium that promotes mitochondrial membrane
625 permeabilization and the subsequent release of cytochrome c into the cytoplasm.
626 Such mitochondrial impairment has been identified as a key initiating event leading to
627 energy depletion and caspase activation in microplastic-exposed fish intestines (Liu et
628 al., 2024; Pei et al., 2025).

629 The specific gene expression and immunofluorescent responses observed in this
630 study further indicate that intestinal inflammation accompanies apoptosis under EMP
631 exposure. The marked increase of *il6* expression and the stronger IL-6 signal within

632 the mucosal layer point to the activation of local cytokine signalling. Comparable
633 patterns have been documented in zebrafish and carp exposed to microplastics,
634 where activation of inflammatory pathways, including NF- κ B signalling, was
635 associated with increased expression of pro-inflammatory genes such as *il6*, *tnfa*, and
636 *il1 β* (Xu et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; Pei et al., 2025). In *D.labrax*, the concomitant
637 increase in apoptotic and inflammatory markers suggests a coordinated intestinal
638 response linking mitochondrial dysfunction to immune activation. This interpretation is
639 consistent with previous studies showing that microplastic induced cellular stress can
640 promote both apoptotic signaling and cytokine production, ultimately contributing to
641 epithelial inflammation (Qiao et al., 2019; Zitouni et al., 2021).

642 Overall, these findings support the view that EMP ingestion disrupts intestinal cellular
643 homeostasis by engaging mitochondrial apoptotic processes together with
644 inflammatory signaling. The combined activation of these responses likely reflects an
645 early mucosal reaction to particle exposure and may, under persistent exposure,
646 contribute to barrier dysfunction and progressive intestinal deterioration.

647 **Metabolomic Profiling Reveals Converging Pathways of Oxidative Stress, Lipid** 648 **Dysregulation**

649 The metabolomic signatures observed in juvenile *Dicentrarchus labrax* following
650 exposure to EMPs indicate extensive disruption of intestinal biochemical homeostasis.
651 Distinct shifts were evident in both exposure groups, encompassing multiple
652 metabolite classes related to lipid remodelling, amino-acid turnover, and oxidative
653 balance. These findings demonstrate that EMP ingestion alters fundamental metabolic
654 pathways, reflecting a coordinated response to physicochemical stress within
655 intestinal tissues.

656 Lipid metabolism emerged as one of the most affected processes, characterized by
657 marked depletion of glycerophospholipids and unsaturated fatty acids in both exposed
658 groups. These metabolites are key structural and functional components of biological
659 membranes and are highly susceptible to oxidative degradation. Their reduction
660 supports the occurrence of EMP-induced lipid peroxidation and membrane
661 destabilization, mechanisms frequently associated with mitochondrial stress (Xu et al.,
662 2023; Liu et al., 2024). This interpretation is further consistent with the gene
663 expression upregulation of *p53* and *Caspase-3*, reflecting activation of intrinsic
664 apoptotic signalling triggered by mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative injury (Lu et
665 al., 2016; Hamed et al., 2021).

666 Alterations in energy metabolism were also evident, but their nature differed between
667 exposure groups. In C1, the presence of carnitine related clusterwithfatty-acid
668 associated changes suggests an early disturbance of mitochondrial fatty acid transport
669 and β -oxidation. Given the central role of carnitine in transferring long-chain fatty acids
670 into mitochondria, these changes are consistent with impaired energy utilization and
671 early bioenergetic stress(Longo et al., 2016).In C2, broader lipid related alterations,
672 including diglycerides, glycerophospholipids, phosphatidylethanolamines, and
673 saturated fatty acids, point to a wide disruption of lipid homeostasis and membrane
674 related metabolism, in line with previous reports of microplastic associated metabolic
675 disturbance (Cappello et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2024). The concurrent increase in
676 *Cytochrome c* and *Caspase-3* expression observed in the present study supports this
677 mechanism, suggesting that EMP exposure promotes bioenergetic imbalance leading
678 to mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis. Perturbations in amino-acid metabolism,
679 particularly those involving glutamate, tryptophan, and tyrosine derivatives, further
680 indicate altered immune and stress signalling. Tryptophan catabolism through the
681 indole pathway produces metabolites that modulate gut immunity. Comparable
682 metabolic responses have been reported in fish exposed to polymeric contaminants,
683 linking indole derivatives with NF- κ B activation and pro-inflammatory cytokine
684 production(Del Piano et al., 2023; Pei et al., 2025). The accumulation of these
685 metabolites in exposed fish corresponds with the elevated immunoreactivity of IL-6
686 and NF- κ B observed by immunofluorescence, reinforcing the interplay between
687 metabolic disturbance and inflammatory activation in the intestine.

688 In C1 fish, several phenolic acids and glycosides were enriched, suggesting an early
689 activation of antioxidant defences. Comparable transient increases in antioxidant
690 metabolites have been described during low-level microplastic exposure in bivalves
691 and fish, preceding oxidative exhaustion at higher doses(Cappello et al., 2021;
692 Missawi et al., 2025).

693 Collectively, these results reveal that EMP exposure impairs lipid homeostasis,
694 mitochondrial function, and redox equilibrium processes tightly coupled with activation
695 of inflammatory and apoptotic signalling in intestinal tissues. The convergence of
696 metabolomic, transcriptomic, and protein-level evidence underscores the intestine's
697 role as a primary and early target of EMP toxicity in fish and highlights the value of
698 integrative omics approaches in elucidating pollutant induced physiological stress.

699 **Multi-Omics Integration and Biological Implications**

700 The joint analysis of metabolomic and metagenomic data provided an integrative view
701 of the intestinal responses of juvenile *Dicentrarchus labrax* to EMPs. The strong
702 covariation detected between metabolic and microbial profiles indicates that EMP
703 exposure perturbs a functionally connected microbial–metabolic network within the
704 gut.

705 Correlations between discriminant features revealed that microbial restructuring and
706 host metabolic adjustments occurred in parallel. Distinct bacterial signatures were
707 associated with the two exposure profiles, with *Acidovorax* linked more closely to C2,
708 whereas *Halioglobus* and *Glaciecola* were more closely associated with C1. These
709 patterns indicate that EMP exposure was accompanied by shifts in bacterial
710 composition occurring alongside changes in intestinal metabolic profiles. Comparable
711 links between microbial restructuring and metabolic disturbance have been reported
712 in other teleost models following microplastic exposure (Qiao et al., 2019; Zhou et al.,
713 2023). Within the integrated model, lipid- and amino-acid-related metabolite features
714 contributed strongly to the separation between exposed groups, indicating that
715 disturbances in these metabolic compartments formed a central component of the
716 intestinal response to EMP exposure. In this context, the differential association of
717 *Acidovorax*, *Halioglobus*, and *Glaciecola* with the exposed groups suggests that EMP
718 exposure reshaped bacterial assemblages in parallel with altered intestinal metabolic
719 homeostasis.

720 Network-level integration further supported this coordinated response, showing that
721 lipid- and amino-acid-related metabolites occupied central positions within the
722 intestinal microbial metabolic network. These cross-domain associations paralleled
723 the molecular patterns observed in the same tissues, where activation of *p53*,
724 *Caspase-3*, and *IL-6* indicated apoptotic and inflammatory signalling. Previous multi-
725 omics studies in aquatic organisms have shown that microplastic exposure can
726 concurrently alter microbial structure, metabolic profiles, and immune related
727 responses (Cappello et al., 2021; Missawi et al., 2025). The present findings extend
728 these observations by showing that, in *Dicentrarchus labrax* exposed to EMPs, gut
729 dysbiosis and metabolic disruption form part of a coordinated intestinal response.

730 **Conclusions**

731 This study demonstrates that exposure to EMPs rapidly impairs intestinal homeostasis
732 in juvenile *Dicentrarchus labrax*. Short-term dietary exposure led to significant
733 retention of particles in gut tissues, with small-sized polyethylene fragments being the

734 most abundant. Multi-omics integration revealed that EMP exposure triggered
735 mitochondrial stress, activating intrinsic apoptotic and inflammatory signalling
736 pathways mediated by p53, Caspase-3, NF- κ B, and IL-6. Metabolomic profiling further
737 indicated disruption of lipid metabolism, and amino acid turnover, consistent with
738 impaired cellular energy regulation and barrier function. Subtle but coordinated shifts
739 in the gut microbial community supported the occurrence of early dysbiosis tightly
740 linked to host metabolic and inflammatory responses.

741 While oxidative stress is a recognized pathway for MP toxicity, we acknowledge that
742 our conclusions are based on pathway inference from multi-omics data. Future studies
743 should include direct quantification of ROS, lipid peroxidation, and antioxidant enzyme
744 activities to mechanistically confirm these observations

745 Collectively, these findings identify the intestine as a sensitive and early target of EMP
746 toxicity and highlight interconnected pathways of inflammation, apoptosis, and
747 microbial imbalance as early indicators of sublethal physiological disturbance. By
748 integrating transcriptomic, metabolomic, and microbial endpoints, this work advances
749 mechanistic understanding of microplastic-induced toxicity in marine fish and provides
750 a framework for developing early biomarkers applicable to ecological risk assessment.

751

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